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High-arctic cultural heritage environments are deteriorated by cruise tourism: a case study from Svalbard

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ABSTRACT

The Arctic's environmental and heritage management authorities face increasing challenges regarding degradation and destruction of natural and cultural heritage, especially due to increasing impacts from tourism and climate change. Tourism is now an important industry in the Arctic, and a major cause of negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity. We assess the different impacts and stressors created by tourism on these areas on the archipelago of Svalbard using field studies and remote sensing. We found that increased tourism during the last three decades (1990–2020) was the most important stressor expressed as impairment of vegetation from 4% to 55% at and around eight major cultural heritage environments on Svalbard. Finally, we outline some future suggestions concerning management and adaption for improvement of sustainable tourism in the High Arctic.

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Cultural heritage; natural heritage; Svalbard; tourism; human disturbance; environmental change

1. Introduction

The Arctic's environmental and heritage management authorities face increasing challenges regarding degradation and destruction of natural and cultural heritage, especially pertaining to impacts from tourism and climate change. The Arctic is changing on multiple levels as the effects of climate and environmental changes are making themselves felt (Box et al., 2019). The Arctic environment is unique and an important attraction for people all over the world. It provides opportunities for experiencing an environment completely different from that which most of us are familiar with. Tourism is now an important and popular industry in the Arctic (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2024) and climate change occurs at a rate four times faster than the rest of the globe (Rantanen et al., 2022). Few studies focus on the effects of cruise tourism on specific ecosystems or species in the High Arctic. Huddart and Stott (2020) identified that the negative impacts of Arctic tourism on species distribution and biodiversity were most pronounced near tourist resorts in northern Finland, Norway and Sweden, while on arctic islands such as Svalbard and Iceland, such impacts were mostly observed at landing and embarking sites for arctic cruise ships. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) have been used to detect and monitor archaeological features on the tundra surface (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015) and subsurface (Walker, 2020).

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The most sensitive plants, birds and mammals show declines or even disappearance from the disturbed areas and the species composition shifts from native 'wild' species to cultural and human associated species (Huddart & Stott, 2020; Tolvanen & Kangas, 2016). Research from across the Arctic region on the spread of alien species shows that it can be promoted through diverse tourism activities, such as hiking, trampling and camping in the mountains of Finland (Tolvanen & Kangas, 2016) and trampling in cultural heritage environments on Arctic cruise destinations in Svalbard and Greenland (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015; Huddart & Stott, 2020). For many visitors, cultural heritage is a main attraction; a cultural heritage that consist of both the human made forms and structures and the surrounding nature in which they are set. Decay is a natural process among cultural heritage environments in general, although the progress or pace differs considerably depending on the nature of natural and human drivers of change. On Svalbard, cultural heritage environments are being strongly affected by human trampling, particularly due to cruise tourism (Figure 1), in addition to the accelerating effects of climate change on natural hazards such as coastal erosion, wind erosion, flooding, thawing, permafrost and bio-deterioration processes (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015; Nicu & Fatorić, 2023). The rapid development of the arctic cruise tourism during the most recent decade has sparked interest and debate concerning restrictions and regulations in the Arctic and particularly so in Svalbard (e.g. Dannevig et al., 2023; Kaltenborn et al. 2024). For Svalbard, Kaltenborn et al. (2024) concluded that the current tourism faces challenges related to several sustainable development goals (SDG) including work conditions, climate change, state of the environment, and management. Dannevig et al. (2023) reviewed and analyzed international and national regulations concerning tourism activities on Svalbard, concluding that a framework is required to maintain natural and environmental goods and services, including restrictions of access to vulnerable areas, for example cultural heritage sites, regulations of organized outdoor activities, and other regulatory measurers and tools. New cruise landing regulations for Svalbard have been set in force from 1 January 2025, however some of them might be changed in the future (see further information in Discussion).

Another debate is the application of social acceptance and trust in terms of cruise tourism. Ólafsdóttir et al. (2024) evaluate the feasibility of using the concept of Social License to Operate (SLO) in Arctic cruise tourism. The evaluation revealed the dominance of cruise companies in

Figure 1. Tourists from a cruise ship onshore in Virgohamna in the beginning of July 2014 - a cultural heritage area in Svalbard.

itinerary planning, with minimal communication among cruise destinations. Economic values and profit often overshadow collaborative planning, leading to varying levels of acceptance among the diverse stakeholders in the cruise tourism destinations depending on the involvement and benefits of tourism and related activities. For SLO to have relevance and legitimacy within cruise and other businesses at the destinations, and among local communities, a continuous flow and circulation of communication and perspectives is critical (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2024).

Due to increasing negative impacts of tourism on Svalbard, the heritage management authorities, administered by the Governor of Svalbard perceived the need to establish a monitoring program to register the effects of tourism and human trampling on cultural heritage monuments and environments to aid management decisions and actions. The aim of this study is to provide to a comprehensive analysis of the impacts on, and stressors of High Arctic natural and cultural heritage sites and areas caused by increasing tourism. We first outline the different impacts and stressors created by tourism on key sensitive cultural heritage areas in Svalbard and discuss direct and indirect mechanisms by which tourism transforms or modifies the sensitive environment in the High Arctic. We then present empirical evidence for the effects of trampling on vegetation and deterioration on cultural heritage environments on Svalbard and the increase in number of tourists during the same period. Finally, we outline some future suggestions concerning monitoring, management and adaptation to a more sustainable tourism in the High Arctic. We create a linkage between ecology, community and history to provide a deeper understanding of the fundamental role of tourism in Arctic ecosystems.

2. Impacts and stressors created by tourism

2.1. *The advent of tourism on Svalbard*

The first evidence of tourism on Svalbard occurred in 1827 in the form of expedition ships that also brought a few tourists with them. The real start of tourism in northern Norway and Svalbard occurred in the 1870's and coincided with the emergence of Tromsø as the preferred port for Arctic research expeditions (Barthelmess, 2007). In 1892, a German called Captain Bade cofounded the 'Nordische Hochseefischerei Gesellschaft' (Nordic Sea Fisheries Company) and was one of the first entrepreneurs who regularly set up cruises to the Svalbard archipelago. The interest in Arctic cruise tourism grew rapidly when the first hotels in Svalbard were built in 1896 and 1897 (Barthelmess, 2007; Reilly, 2009). This first wave of tourism lasted until the start of the First World War in 1914. The next wave of tourism occurred between the 1960s and 1980s with cruise companies such as the Norwegian America Line (Pedersen & Hawks, 1996). This, coupled with the development of a new airport in 1975, and hotels in Longyearbyen, sparked the start of the major growth in the tourist industry through to the present day. In 1994 there were thought to be around 30,000 visitors to Svalbard (Huddart & Stott, 2020). In 1997 there were around 39,000 cruise passengers ashore at 76 landing sites (MOSJ, 2023) and in 2009 around 101,000 at 163 landing sites. In 2014 this had increased to 131,000 visitors at 195 landing sites, and Svalbard had become the most visited place in the Arctic (The Control and Constitution Committee of Norway, 2007; Huddart & Stott, 2020).

2.2. *Impacts on vegetation in cultural heritage areas*

Going ashore is an important part of a cruise program for the arctic expedition operators sailing around Svalbard and is central to the nature interpretation work of guides (Huddart & Stott, 2020). Hiking around the settlements of Longyearbyen, Ny Ålesund and Barentsburg is also popular amongst tourists and locals. The sites and environments visited differ in landforms and vegetation, but in many places sensitive tundra vegetation begins close to the shore or the settlements. A study found that terrestrial vegetation zones on Svalbard with the highest biodiversity values are mostly located in unprotected areas, and where substantial human activity takes place (Hagen, Vistad, et al., 2012). Hence, trampling pressure may lead to direct reduction of fragile Svalbard tundra vegetation

in areas of biological hotspots (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015). Furthermore, through increased use of easily accessible landing sites and pathways around the settlements, there is a higher risk of introducing non-native plants, especially to these areas (Bartlett et al., 2021).

3. Empirical evidence for negative effects of tourism on vegetation and monuments at cultural heritage environments

3.1. Materials and methods

3.1.1. Selection of environments

We selected eight environments located in central and northwestern Spitsbergen (Figure 2) based on the following criteria: a) environments encompassed cultural heritage representative of the human history on Svalbard, b) sites were affected by known stressors such as deterioration from tourism, and climate change and c) environments that, with one exception of Gjøanes are, or have been popular tourist destinations back to the late 19th century (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015). Among the sites that met our criteria, the final choice concerning seven of them was made based on discussions with the Cultural Heritage

Figure 2. The study area of the north-western and central part of Svalbard. The sites consist of seven cultural environments encompassing cultural heritage covering the range of human history in Svalbard, and one site, Platåfjellet which has been a popular hiking trail close to Longyearbyen for decades.

Directorate and the Governor of Svalbard, while the last (Platåfjellet in Longyearbyen) was selected to assess the deterioration by trampling made by both tourists and inhabitants of Longyearbyen. In all but two of the environments, London and Platåfjellet, we find a high number of cultural heritage structures and objects reminiscent of whaling, especially the early phases of whaling during the first half of the 17th century. In and around London and Platåfjellet we find a broad range of structures left behind by mining activities in the 20th century. Generally, environmental hazards (e.g. landslides and avalanches), biological degradation, wildlife and human activity may be regarded as the primary degradation parameters for cultural heritage in Svalbard (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015). Coastal erosion, sand drift, and wind erosion are primary environmental impact factors at most of the sites. Currently, disembarkation from tourism is not well regulated and can occur almost anywhere across the Svalbard islands. Both climate change and the growth in tourism are expected to continue, increasing the threat to cultural heritage in Svalbard. As the number of visitors has increased at London, Virgohamna and Smeerenburg in recent decades, human activity has become an impact factor that must be considered. In London, the number of visitors increased from less than 100 to 1200 in 2009 with a subsequent increase to 2800 in 2014 (Hagen et al., 2015). Platåfjellet is promoted as a popular and easy-access destination near Longyearbyen by Visit Norway. The environment of Gjøaneset, on the other hand, is not promoted and little known, while on the graveyards in Likneset and Gravneset, a traffic ban is imposed. Gjøaneset and Likneset are closed as landing sites (Governor of Svalbard, 2024).

3.1.2. Data collection and analysis

We have used remote sensing data and complemented these with ground-based surveys to assess the impacts and stressors on vegetation. Statistical data concerning the number of tourists onshore in the landing places on Svalbard is provided by MOSJ (2025).

3.1.3. Field work

The ground-based surveys at the seven key sites (Figure 2) were carried out in 2014, while Platåfjellet (Figure 2) was surveyed twice, in 2010 and 2014 (Hagen et al., 2015). The objective of the surveys was to identify and document physical evidence of recent human activity, to assess the natural and anthropogenic drivers of environmental change, and to evaluate the vulnerability of the cultural heritage environments. The ground-based survey was undertaken to assess the current state of the cultural heritage environment and to develop indicators useful for monitoring changes in the state of the cultural heritage environments within the study area. The ground-based general survey was primarily focused on assessing the current state of the cultural heritage environment on a general level, and on providing a knowledge basis for developing indicators useful for monitoring cultural heritage environments located in High Arctic environments (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015). The sites were walked and surveyed, data gathering was focused on identifying and documenting evidence of recent human activity using ordinary digital photographs of the various natural and anthropogenic impacts. Further the vulnerability of cultural heritage assets was assessed. The state of the vegetation was surveyed using ordinary plot imagery (RBG) including near-infrared measurements (NIR) for visual analysis of the status of vegetation cover and description of the vegetation species content in each plot (50×50 cm) along transects covering the entire heritage area. These surveys also provided ground-truthing information for the calibration of the remote sensed imagery used, and here RBG- and NIR-imagery from the surface was assessed and compared with the airborne and/or spaceborne imageries (Parcak, 2009; Thuestad et al. 2015). A summary of key characteristics and current threats to the cultural and natural environments are shown in Table 1.

3.1.4. Remote sensing

Remotely sensed data from eight sites (see Table 1) were analyzed and proposed to be impacted by tourism by the Norwegian Polar Institute. The Governor of Svalbard was contacted and acquired to

Table 1. Natural and cultural heritage environments representative of Svalbard's historic periods, archaeological features and known threats or impact factors on the environment. Included is data from Platåfjellet hiking trail in Longyearbyen which is used by both residents and tourists. Based partly on own knowledge and sources like Arlov (2003, Dahle et al. (2000), and Sandodden et al. (2013).

Environment	Original function and use period	Main features	Current threats	Measures
Platåfjellet – Longyearbyen	Hiking trail from 1900 to present. Heavily used by tourists (summer) and year around by locals	Iconic view over Longyearbyen and the Isfjorden area	Human activity, trampling, vegetation deterioration and erosion. Partly influenced by air pollution from the electrical power plant and cruise ships and/or vessels	Planned or suggested measures e.g. Sherpa-trail or wooden paths. Reduced cruise traffic by large ships.
Sallyhamna	Whaling: 1600–1700s Hunting: 1937–1940s	Whaling station: four blubber ovens, two with a secondary grave on top, single grave, road, and building ruins. Hunting station: a standing trapper's cabin from the 1900s.	Coastal erosion Human activity	None
London	Mining	Marble mining settlement	Coastal erosion Human activity	Reduced cruise passenger ashore
Likneset	Whaling: 1650–1750s	Largest graveyard in Svalbard with 225 recorded graves	Coastal erosion, thawing processes, melt water	Closed off to visitors in 2010
Gjøanes	Whaling: 1600–1700s	Observation post with building ruins, fireplaces, camp site, two graveyards and several single graves	Coastal erosion	Not used as embarkation site
Smeerenburg	Whaling: 1610–1660	Whaling station: eight blubber ovens, 19 house sites, graveyard with 101 recorded graves.	Coastal erosion, human activity, and sand drift.	None
Virgohamna	Whaling: 1600s Scientific and explorative efforts: late 1800s–early 1900s Tourism: since 1888	Whaling station: three blubber ovens, graveyard with approximately 12 graves Expedition and scientific bases (Andrée and Wellman) with ruins, memorial, living quarters, hydrogen production facilities, balloon- and airship hangar, 'Pike's' house	Human activity, thawing processes, melt water	Embarkation in Virgohamna was regulated in 2000
Gravneset	Whaling: 1600–1700s Tourism: 1800s onwards	Whaling station: four blubber ovens, graveyard with approximately 130 graves	Coastal erosion, human activity, sand drift	Graveyard was partly fenced in 1996, fully fenced off in 2002

run an analysis of potential impacts of tourism around the archipelago (Sandodden, 2013; Sandodden, Tokle, & Solli, 2013). These included the seven key cultural heritage environments chosen for ground surveys. The remotely sensing data was sourced from digital aerial photographs (1990 and 2009 – 2011), UAV-borne (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle called Cryowing) acquired in 2014 and high-resolution satellite imagery acquired by WorldView-2/3 in 2011, 2013 and 2016 (Table 2). The identification of structures and objects was based on aerial and satellite image data encompassing three-band (NIR-R-G) imagery from 1990 and four-band (R-G-B-NIR) imagery with a ground spatial resolution of 50 cm all other years (Table 2). The latter data was based on the Airborne Vexcel

Table 2. Remote sensing data comprising aerial sensors and spaceborne sensors used in the study. The RGB color is an additive color model in which the red, green and blue primary colors of light are fused in various ways to reproduce a broad array of colors. NIR= near infrared band, PAN= a panchromatic image is made when the imaging sensor becomes sensitive to large amounts of lights or wavelengths in the visible spectrum. Pan sharpened band uses a higher-resolution panchromatic image to fuse with a lower-resolution multiband raster dataset. The result produces a multiband raster dataset with the resolution of the panchromatic raster and gives often better details than a multiband raster set alone.

Sensor	Date, year	Spatial resolution	Bands	Comments
Aerial photographs (digital)	July–August 1990	50 cm	NIR-R-G	Scanned film in three bands by The Norwegian Polar Institute.
Airborne Vexcel Ultracam sensor	July–August 2009–2010	50 cm	R-G-B-NIR	Usually used as the main sensor for Norway and Svalbard for aerial photo monitoring.
WorldView-2	05-08-2011	50 cm	R-G-B- NIR	Bands 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 + PAN, a PAN-sharpened version is applied in this study.
WorldView-2	15-08-2012	50 cm	R-G-B- NIR	Bands 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 + PAN, a PAN-sharpened version is applied in this study.
WorldView-2	13-08-2013 31-08-2013	50 cm	R-G-B- NIR	Bands 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 + PAN, a PAN-sharpened version is applied in this study.
UAV RGB	Early July 2014	2–5 cm	RGB	Canon Powershot imagery; resampled to 50 cm for the reflectance analysis and classification. Resampled to 50 cm
WorldView-3	10-08-2016	30 cm	R-G-B- NIR	Bands 2,3,4,5,6 and 7 + PAN, A PAN-sharpened version is applied in this study. Resampled to 50 cm.

Ultracam sensor data (RGB-NIR). The payload of the Cryowing consisted of a commercial Canon EOS-M digital camera with a fixed 22 mm lens, which corresponds to a ground resolution of 2–5 cm at a flight altitude of 120 m above ground level.

The different imageries have been visually analyzed for traces of human activity using the software ENVI and ArcGIS. This software has also been used to carry out different vegetation classification algorithms, indices and changes in vegetation detection methods (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015). In addition, field measurements were used in the delineation of the area exposed to trampling and deterioration (see Field work). We identified the WorldView-2 (WV-2) sensor as the master sensor since it is better calibrated by the producers than the other and older sensors (Lv et al., 2022). The 1990 and the 2009–2016 imageries were classified using a supervised maximum likelihood classification by calculating the following discriminant functions for each pixel in the image (Richards & Jia, 2005; Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015):

$$g_i(x) = \ln p(\omega_i) - \frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \sum_j i \right| - \frac{1}{2} (x - m_j) \sum_i^{-1} (x - m_j)$$

Where: i = class, x = n-dimensional data (where n is the number of bands), $p(\omega_i)$ = probability that class ω_i occurs in the image and is assumed to be the same for all classes, $|\sum_i|$ = determinant of the covariance matrix of the data in class ω_i , \sum_i^{-1} = its inverse matrix and m_i = mean vector. From the resulting vegetation cover maps, we calculated and assessed the area of deterioration (m^2) and percentage of area with deterioration for each environment for each year of data.

4. Results

4.1. Vegetation deterioration and damage at pristine and cultural heritage environments

Deterioration of cultural heritage objects and their surrounding areas are apparent when looking at Figure 3, indicating the area where one blubber oven has already been lost and another is on the way to being destroyed by trampling of tourists (own observation June 2014) in combination with coastal

Figure 3. Coastal erosion and deterioration by trampling of tourists on a blubber oven from the whaling period (17th century) in Smeerenburg.

Figure 4. Virgohamna 2009: airborne sensor vexcel image over the heritage site., deterioration of vegetation is shown in bright colours on and along tracks leading up to the monument which is encircled.

erosion. A blubber oven is an oven that produces oil from the blubber of the whale, which is a thick layer of vascularized lipid-rich fiber-laced tissue under the skin of all whales. Anthropogenic disturbance has increased as the number of tourists disembarking in areas outside of the settlements such as Virgohamna (Figure 4) and in Isfjorden has increased dramatically during the last three decades (Table 3). These disembarkations, which primarily take place during the summer season increased by nearly 300% from 1996 to 2019. The figures were quite stable from 1996 until 2000; thereafter, the number of tourists going ashore rose by around 72%.

Detection of the extent of deterioration and erosion at the key ground truthing environments on Svalbard between 1990 and 2016 is presented in Table 4. Most of the environments have been

Table 3. Total number of cruise ship disembarkation sites in Svalbard and the total number of disembarkations outside the settlements Longyearbyen, Ny ålesund-London, Barentsburg, Hornsund and Pyramiden and locations in Isfjorden, for selected years over a 20-y period (1996–2016). Source: MOSJ (2023).

Year	People ashore #	Disembarkation sites #	People: increase since 1996%)	Sites: increase since 1996%)
1996	29340	53		
2000	29483	94	<0.1	77.4
2005	63549	167	116.6	215.1
2007	62433	138	112.8	160,4
2008	64303	136	119.2	156.6
2009	65619	140	123.6	164.2
2010	59581	146	103.1	175.4
2011	53431	153	82.1	188.7
2012	62641	176	113.5	232.1
2013	65523	189	123.3	256.6
2014	60181	169	105.1	218.9
2015	84104	179	186.7	237.7
2016	81921	208	179.2	292.4

Table 4. Area of deterioration and trampling damage to vegetation in m² (percent of area in parenthesis) for the eight environments in Svalbard during the period 1990–2016, based on satellite classified imagery.

Year	Platåfjellet	Gravneset	Smeerenburg	London	Sallyhamna	Likneset	Gjøaneset	Virgohamna
1990	3464.8 (3.5)	26770.0 (64.1)	448.5 (36.3)	827.5 (1.3)	2781 (26.9)	4251 (3.9)	302 (4.5)	246920 (8.7)
2009–2010	19612.8 (19.6)	15025.0 (36.0)	540.0 (43.7)	7909.6 (12.6)	2613 (25.4)	18850 (17.3)		896290 (31.8)
2011						16894 (15.5)	580 (.8.66)	975895 (34.6)
2012			477.0 (38.6)					
2013		10057.0 (24.1)		29798.8 (47.4)				
2014			939.8 (76.1)	45104.4 (71.7)	1841 (17.9)		580 (8.6)	975895 (34.6)
2016				35288.7 (56.1)				

heavily affected by a combination of trampling and deterioration of vegetation from the increasing numbers of tourists, and coastal erosion (Table 4). There is a gradual ongoing deterioration with respect to the base year 1990 (first year with airborne NIR-imagery) of the vegetation cover within many cultural heritage environments and along access trails as well as deterioration of several cultural heritage objects, especially in London, Smeerenburg (Figure 3, Table 4), Likneset and Virgohamna (Table 4). For example, the deterioration of the vegetation and environment has increased from 8.7% to 34.6% of the area around Virgohamna (Figure 4) in the period 1990 to 2014 (Table 4), while in London the deterioration and erosion by trampling (Figures 5,6) have increased from 1.3% in 1990 to 47.4% in 2013 with a subsequently increase to 56.1% in 2016. For Smeerenburg and Likneset, ongoing coastal erosion is rapid (Table 4). However, for Smeerenburg an increase in vegetation is experienced. The higher amount of deterioration and damage in London in 2014 compared with 2016 may be due to early image acquisition (first week of July) for 2014 compared to the WV-3 image acquired in August 2016, hence the vegetation was more developed for the latter image. The vegetation has also deteriorated on-, and along the hiking trail up to Platåfjellet in Longyearbyen, shown by an increase in deterioration from 3.5% to almost 20% between 1990 and 2011 (Table 4). The number of visitors in most areas has risen from a few dozen in the mid-1990's to several thousand visitors annually (Table 3). In Gravneset (Magdalenafjorden), however, we can observe the opposite situation with reduced deterioration since the graveyard was fenced off for visitors in 1996, resulting in a reduced human footprint and deterioration from 64% in 1990 to 24% in 2013 (Table 4). In Sallyhamna, which was a hunting station until 1973, the situation has improved concerning deterioration (Table 4).

Figure 5. Deterioration and erosion on a path used by tourists in London, July 2014.

Figure 6. London photographed by UAV (drone) in July 2014. Areas of deterioration and erosion show up as light/bright tracks from the beach, areas around the cottages and the cultural remains in the right side of the picture. We have marked these tracks with red arrows.

4.2. Deterioration and damage to cultural heritage monuments and objects

Cultural heritage in Svalbard has been and will continue to be subject to transformation and decay through a multitude of environmental and human-induced processes. Management authorities on all levels are aware of the ongoing changes and degradation, and there is a clear recognition that it is not possible to conserve all, or even most of the cultural heritage in the archipelago in the long term. Biodeterioration in wooden heritage, for instance, cannot

Figure 7. A grave at Likneset in danger of being washed to sea due to erosion. Photo: Alma Thuestad, NIKU.

realistically be stopped (Flyen & Thuestad, 2023). The Governor of Svalbard has thus selected 100 cultural heritage environments that are prioritized regarding protection and conservation measures (Sandodden et al., 2013). Occasionally, one of the few feasible measures is excavation to preserve knowledge that otherwise would be lost such as at Likneset (Loktu & Vivås, 2022) where whaler's graves are threatened by erosion (Figure 7). This and other archaeological excavations and investigations have shown that the environmental changes in Svalbard in recent decades have significant negative impacts on the preservation conditions for cultural heritage in the archipelago.

Wear and deterioration to cultural heritage objects from people walking on and through the cultural monuments is evident, for example on some of the wooden remains of buildings and machine halls in London. Deterioration from human traffic through building remains could also be seen in Virgohamna and Smeerenburg. In comparison, objects and structures such as pottery and graves at Gjøanes, appeared undisturbed by recent human activity.

Human-induced processes are a significant threat, but management authorities have more options when it comes to preventing or managing human impact on cultural heritage. The measures taken at Gravneset, where human traffic within the graveyard was restricted led to a reduced human footprint and deterioration (Table 4) and show the value of proactive management. Svalbard is economically reliant on tourism at the same time as tourism is seen as a threat to the environment if not managed. Legislative changes are underway in Svalbard that hold the potential to change the scope and conditions of tourism in multiple ways (Justis- og beredskapsdepartementet, 2024; Dannevig et al., 2023). As we steadily see more clearly the effects of climate change, choices will have to be made regarding our activities in the Arctic. The basis for sound management is knowledge of ongoing environmental and cultural heritage processes.

5. Discussion

5.1. Assessment of the deterioration

Our analysis shows that there are significant increases in damage to both vegetation and heritage environments used as landing sites for expedition cruise ships on Svalbard. Most of this damage is due to trampling on and around cultural heritage environments and viewpoints. Such deterioration and damage are especially apparent in areas such as Smeerenburg, London, Virgohamna and

Platåfjellet. Some areas, for example, Likneset and Smeerenburg, were also negatively affected by the combined effects of coastal erosion and permafrost thaw and might be similar with ongoing erosion and damage to the cultural heritage site in Hiorthamn (Nicu, Rubensdotter, et al., 2021). Parmentier et al. (2024) have reported extensive vegetation damage due to permafrost subsidence and gullying in Adventdalen. Since the future climate is expected to be warmer on Svalbard (Vikhamar-Schuler et al., 2016), the combination of warming (Bjerke et al., 2017) and increased trampling from tourists may accelerate vegetation deterioration (Tolvanen & Kangas, 2016).

An opposite development can be observed for the environment Gravneset in Magdalenafjorden. This environment was heavily visited in the first wave of tourism in the period 1880 – 1914 followed by a decadal increase of visits by arctic expedition cruise ships in the period 1960 – 1990. The detrimental effects on the graveyard during the last period forced the authorities to fence it off in 1996 (Barlindhaug et al., 2017; Johansen et al., 2010), hence the vegetation has shown a strong recovery. In addition, this environment has had an increase of thermophilous vascular plants during the last decades (Arnesen et al., 2014; Engelskjøn et al., 2003). Despite the ongoing coastal erosion is rapid in Smeerenburg an increase in vegetation is observed. Van der Knaap (1985) reported that a dense moss cover of the moss *Drepanocladus* was reestablished before 1985, suggesting a low nutrient level of the substrate. The density of the moss cover and the appearance of taxa that grow on moist (*Pohlia albicans*) or wet (*Calliergon trifarium*) soils indicate that the soil in the area has become much moister (Van der Knaap (1985) and this cover of the same mosses still exists and have increased in cover the last decades up to 2014. Shell fragments in the upper three soil sections suggest frequent flooding. The absence of salt-resistant taxa in the vegetation indicates that the source of this flooding is the neighbouring fresh-water lagoon in Smeerenburg (Van der Knaap (1985), and this may be the reason for the increase in the moss and vegetation cover the last decades.

For London, Hagen et al. (2015) reported a minor reduced vegetation trend especially in lichen cover in permanent vegetation plots during 2009 – 2014, possibly related to trampling. They found a positive relationship between the total vegetation cover and near-surface NDVIs of the same plots. However, plots with the same cover had a large range in NDVI so this index is not well qualified to uncover early effects of deterioration or trampling.

5.2. Monitoring and management of sensitive ecosystems

The existing literature on animal responses to human disturbance provides an adequate foundation for identifying measures that can protect wildlife, and natural and cultural environments in the Arctic (Hagen, Vistad, et al., 2012, Hagen, Erikstad, & Bakkestuen, 2012; Huddart & Stott, 2020). Site-specific management must be founded on knowledge about species abundance and properties of each environment and such information is sparse (Hagen, Vistad, et al., 2012). It is crucial to ensure that these factors are included when selecting environments for monitoring. In a report to the Governor of Svalbard, Barlindhaug et al. (2017) present a thorough review and discussion of relevant indicators for monitoring. In Table 5, we present the results from this discussion, which is a list of proposed indicators with associated parameters for monitoring. These indicators can also be used in other areas of the arctic and boreal regions of Fennoscandia. For the cultural heritage environments and other environmentally sensitive areas, further monitoring needs to be targeted towards highlighting changes over time in locations with several remains and at singular cultural monuments in addition to natural conservation areas.

New cruise landing regulations for Svalbard following up proposals in Hagen, Vistad, et al. (2012), Huddart and Stott (2020), Hovelsrud et al. (2023) have been enacted from 1 January 2025: 'The regulation means that landing for tourist activities can only take place at specific, mapped locations. In addition, landing and staying on land can only take place together with a guide with knowledge of the natural and cultural environment. The regulation also regulates how many people can be on land at the same time' (Governor of Svalbard, 2024). This will hopefully, together with future monitoring be a measure to regulate and reduce the negative impacts of tourism on the landing sites we have included in this paper.

Table 5. Relevant indicators and parameters for monitoring cultural heritage environments and natural conservation areas.

Cultural monuments and natural conservation areas		Parameter		
Indicator	Natural conservation areas	Cultural monuments and environments	New unwanted elements	Lost or displaced smaller objects at a environment
Human drivers	Changes in vegetation-status on a defined disturbed area within a environment. Greening around settlements and dog safari sites, settlements. Invasive (alien) plants and species Air pollution and noise pollution by cruise ships	Changes in construction details of cultural monuments. Deterioration to monuments and conservation areas	Camping sites, hearths, settlements, spread of invasion or alien plants. Increased noise in the settlements (on land) Increased noise in the fjords (underwater noise).	Household effects, remains of equipment, machines, jerry cans, etc. Seaborne waste; litter and plastics
Natural drivers	Vegetation: Changes caused by changing climatic factors like temperature or precipitation. Winter warming events Sea/Coastal erosion: Changing distance from specific points to the escarpment Eroded vegetation Landslides	Melt water: Erosion or humidity damage caused by melt water dependent on distance to escarpments and slope	Frequency of landslide, erosion and coastal erosion events	

In addition to human trampling, we also need to consider natural pressures such as coastal erosion (Thuestad, Tømmervik, & Solbø, 2015; Thuestad, Tømmervik, Solbø, Barlindhaug, et al., 2015), melting of permafrost, wind erosion, and landslides (that may affect both cultural heritage and natural conservation environments) and to be able to distinguish between natural and human-based drivers for deterioration of cultural heritage areas. A recent climatic trend is the winter warming events that lead to increased risk (Bjerke et al., 2017; Vikhamar-Schuler et al., 2016). Also, natural hazards such as coastal erosion, meltwater and higher temperatures are some of the most relevant drivers for landslides and subsidence of permafrost (Rouyet et al., 2019; Parmentier et al. 2024; Nicu, Lombardo, et al., 2021; Nicu, Rubensdotter, Stalsberg, & Nau, 2021), and increased climatically induced vegetation mortality (Bjerke et al., 2017). All these factors induce increased erosion to cultural heritage monuments and areas. New methods such as ground penetrating radars (GPR) have been shown to be efficient in mapping subsurface wooden remains in Svalbard (Tavakoli et al., 2023). Air pollution by cruise vessels which contaminate soil and vegetation might lead to higher sensitivity for drivers such as trampling and climatic deterioration (Elberling et al., 2007).

The work of Hovelsrud et al. (2023) which proposed a framework of natural and environmental considerations and regulations of organized outdoor activities might be used in combination with the new governor regulations in action from January 2025. SLO evaluation (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2024) can additionally be used for disturbances like deterioration of vegetation in natural- and cultural heritage areas. However, plans and SLO-processes must be open, transparent and well-circulated between cruise operators, stakeholders and authorities (Ólafsdóttir et al., 2024) for the maintenance of sustainability in the tourism industry in Svalbard and other places in the Arctic.

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